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Figure 72.1. Kaplan-Meier curves of cardiac, non-cardiac and all-cause death for patients stratified according to the 'VLF-dependent' and 'VLF-independent'

Results: Figure shows cumulative cardiac, non-cardiac and all-cause mortality curves for the patients classified by the 'VLF-dependent' and 'VLF-independent'.

Conclusion: the 'VLF-dependent' proves to be a significant predictor of cardiac death, whereas the 'VLF-independent' predicts non-cardiac death - the combination of both indices stratifies all-cause mortality. Thus, the analysis of the validation cohort confirmed principal findings of our previous study.

and papillary muscles. Final segmentation threshold is determined by analysis of intensity distributions in the located ROI.

Results and Conclusions: Proposed automatic ROI definition algorithm successfully locates the heart region in practically all images, while subsequent automatic right ventricle segmentation algorithm was able to obtain the necessary ventricle information in all imaging planes except those near the apex and base of the heart. These regions exhibit significant differences in intensity statistics and appearance of the ventricle while contributing little to true ventricle volume. The proposed automatic segmentation approach is therefore an efficient alternative for extracting the right ventricle in MR images (completing in less than a minute) compared to manually segmented images, requiring significantly longer effort. Focus of future work will be on constructing more robust algorithms for near-apex and near-base slices able to model their specific local properties.

AN APPROACH TO RIGHT VENTRICLE SEGMENTATION IN MR IMAGES

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Introduction: Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is considered a reference modality for non-invasive assessment of cardiac morphology and function. Important information on the heart's contractility can be obtained from cine MRI images using the short-axis view. MRI image processing implies segmentation of cardiac ventricles as a prerequisite for evaluation of ventricular function. Variability among subjects makes subjective ventricle segmentation a difficult and time consuming task. We show how a computer vision approach can be used to automatically segment the right ventricle, particularly demanding for its characteristic morphology.

Methods: MRI images used were acquired at the Diagnostic Imaging Centre, Oncology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia. Automatic segmentation initialises by locating a region of interest (ROI) containing the heart, using morphological activity detection between consecutive cardiac cycle frames. Due to extremely thin wall of the right ventricle intensity based segmentation is difficult. To overcome this problem, we use robust adaptive contrast adjustment that maximizes separation of bright blood volumes and dark cardiac wall

74. PROSPECTIVE VALIDATION OF AUTOMATED RIGHT VENTRICULAR OVERDRIVE PACING FOR SIMPLIFIED DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF SUPRAVENTRICULAR TACHYCARDIAS IN CHILDREN AND ADULTS

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